

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE PROGRESSION AND PROGNOSIS OF NONSPECIFIC AORTOARTERITIS WITH DIFFERENT TREATMENT APPROACHES

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Summary. *The purpose of the work: comparative assessment of the progression and prognosis of nonspecific aortoarteritis (NAA) with different treatment approaches. Were observed 300 patients. Thus, we believe that it is necessary to determine the stage of the process according to clinical and laboratory signs, however, given the diversity and multiplicity of lesions in NAA, all patients with a chronic stage should undergo pulse therapy in a hospital before surgery, and if there is no need for surgery, pulse therapy and methotrexate for 3 months. All patients with diagnosed acute and subacute stages should receive pulse therapy and methotrexate parenterally for at least 3 months, after which they can be operated on. This indicates that in NAA, inflammation is permanent, but expressed to varying degrees, and the chronic stage is conditional. Threshold levels for laboratory remission of NAA: ESR is less than 21 mm/h, CRP is less than 11 mg/l at AUC = 0.91 (sensitivity =90%, specificity =85%) and 0.88 (sensitivity =95%, specificity =80%), respectively. Evidence was obtained on the effectiveness of pulse therapy at any stage of NAA, which proved 1) the permanence of inflammation and the conditionality of the chronic stage, 2) the negative effect of surgery without prior pulse therapy, since the progression of NAA against the background of pulse therapy decreased 4.3 times with conservative (from 26.3% to 6.1%) and 3.8 times (from 49.4% to 13.1%) during surgical treatment. The treatment strategy for all patients with NAA consists in prescribing pulse therapy with cyclophosphane and methylprednisolone: both in the chronic stage and in the presence of indications for surgery, as well as in the acute and subacute stages. This strategy has made it possible to stabilize inflammation, control the disease and prevent complications.*

Key words: *nonspecific aortoarteritis (NAA), puls-therapy with using high doses of cyclophosphane and methylprednisolone, methotrexate.*

Introduction. Nonspecific aortoarteritis (NAA), or Takayasu arteritis, more often begins in adolescence in girls and has a progressive course, causing occlusive lesions of the branches of the aortic arch, which occupy the second place after atherosclerosis in frequency [1]. The natural course of the disease leads to the fact that autoimmune granulomatous vasculitis in the aorta and its branches, passing from adventitia to the entire thickness of the artery wall, accompanied by inflammatory attacks, gradually leads to narrowing of the vessel lumen and the development of ischemia [2], and in terms of up to 10 years from the onset of the disease, 70% of patients have complications: cerebrovascular insufficiency, vasorenal hypertension, ischemia of the upper extremities, etc [4,7].

To diagnose the activity of the process in NAA, a number of evaluation scales have been proposed, the most commonly used of which is ITAS-2010 [3]. Radiation imaging methods (ultrasound duplex scanning (US-DS), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), multispiral computed tomography (MSCT), positron emission computed tomography (PET-CT) are the main methods of diagnosing the localization and activity of the process in NAA [6]. Each of the methods has its advantages and limitations [8]. Of the laboratory research methods for determining the activity of the process, the determination of C-reactive protein (CRP) and the erythrocyte sedimentation rate

(ESR) are the most informative, it is also proposed to determine those molecules that are produced locally in an inflamed vessel, reflecting the degree of inflammation (proinflammatory cytokines, pentraxin-3 (PTX-3) [1,3]. Glucocorticosteroids (GCS), cytostatics, and targeted anti-cytokine drugs are used in the treatment of NAA, however, to date there has not been a single randomized clinical trial proving the effectiveness of any of the following drugs: methotrexate, azathioprine, mofetil mycophenolate, cyclosporine, leflunomide, inflixumab, tocilizumab [5,9].

Purpose of the work: comparative assessment of the progression and prognosis of nonspecific aortoarteritis with different treatment approaches.

Methods. Depending on the approach to diagnosis and treatment, all patients were divided into 2 groups. Group I (comparison group) included patients hospitalized in the period 1978-2004, group II (main group) included patients who received treatment in 2005-2021. There were 159 patients in group I, 15 men (9.4%), 144 women (90.6%). The average age of the patients was 30.5 ± 0.71 years. In group I, 83 (52.2%) patients underwent various types of surgical interventions, and 76 (47.8%) patients received conservative therapy. There were 141 patients in group II, of whom 13 (9.2%) were men and 128 (90.8%) were women. The average age of patients was 31.6 ± 0.77 years; 76 (53.9%) patients underwent various types of surgical interventions, 65 (46.1%) patients received conservative therapy. In group I patients, after verification of the NAA stage and localization of the lesion by imaging methods, management tactics were determined. Patients with acute and subacute stages in need of surgical treatment were treated with glucocorticosteroids to suppress the activity of the process, after which surgical intervention was performed. Patients in the chronic stage of NAA who have indications for surgery were operated immediately after diagnosis.

Results. Of the 159 patients in group I, 155 (97.5%) received GCS before admission from the hospital, moreover, only 67 (42%) patients regularly took GCS at a dose of 1 mg / kg / day, 38 (23.9%) received GCS periodically, having low adherence to treatment. At the time of admission, the acute stage was in 100 (62.9%), subacute – in 33 (20.7%), chronic – in 26 (16.4%) patients. All patients with acute and subacute stages were prescribed 1mg/kg GCS therapy for 1-2 months. 76 patients had no indications for surgery, because vascular stenoses were hemodynamically insignificant, or in the presence of GDSS, clinical manifestations regressed against the background of conservative treatment. Nevertheless, in the dynamics of these 76 patients, against the background of conservative treatment, the progression of the process was in 20 patients (26.3%), while on repeated examination after 3-6 months, additional vascular damage by radiation imaging was revealed in the form of hemodynamically insignificant stenosis in 7 (9.2%) and hemodynamically significant stenosis in 13 (17.1%) of patients. Despite this, none of these patients required surgery.

Indications for surgery were in 83 patients, and 61 (73.5%) had acute, 12 (14.5%) had subacute, and only 10 (12%) had chronic stage of NAA. Patients with the chronic stage were operated directly during the current hospitalization, patients with the acute and subacute stages received conservative treatment with GCS for 1-2 months, after which they underwent surgical interventions. After surgical treatment, the progression of NAA in the form of involvement of new vessels was observed in 41 patients (49.4%), with hemodynamically insignificant stenosis GDSS in 9 (10.8%), hemodynamically significant stenosis GDSS in 32 (38.6%).

A comparative analysis of the progression of NAA against the background of conservative and surgical treatment showed that surgery performed against the background of inflammation significantly worsens the course of NAA, causing the progression of vascular lesions in the form

of hemodynamically significant stenosis in various vascular domains and involving new vessels (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Progression of NAA involving new segments and arteries in group I

Considering that based on clinical and laboratory data, it is possible to determine the stage of the process only conditionally, in group II we applied a pulse therapy scheme using high doses of cyclophosphane and methylprednisolone, developed by A.V. Pokrovsky, which was supplemented and modified by us and proved to be highly effective. All patients of group II with diagnosed acute and subacute received pulse therapy and methotrexate parenterally for at least 3 months according to the scheme (1st day - 1000 mg of cyclophosphane and 1000 mg of methylprednisolone (Solu-Medrol) intravenously per 150 ml of saline solution, heparin 5000 IU / k every 6 hours (4 times a day); on the 2nd and 3rd days - 1000 mg of methylprednisolone (Solu-Medrol) intravenously, heparin 5000 IU / k every 6 hours (4 times a day); from 4 days to 3 months – methotrexate ("METORTHRIT") 1.5 ml subcutaneously (15mg) 1 time per week; from 4 days: double anticoagulation therapy (antiplatelet+anticoagulant) acetylsalicylic acid (Cardiomagnil) 75 mg / day and rivaroxaban (Xarelto) 20 mg / day daily for 6 months; from 3 to 6 months: methotrexate tablets 1 time per week for 15 mg (15 mg / week)). If the first course of pulse therapy is ineffective, the second and third courses of pulse therapy with cyclophosphane and methylprednisolone are carried out with an interval of 7 days. Further, the patient received maintenance therapy with methotrexate in combination with antiplatelet agents/anticoagulants for 6 months. The patient is under observation, at least once every 3 months, an examination and determination of inflammatory markers are carried out: ESR, CRP. If there are indications for surgery, the intervention should be carried out no earlier than 3 months after conservative treatment of NAA.

All patients with a chronic stage, if there were indications for surgery, underwent pulse therapy in a hospital before the intervention. For the chronic stage, if there were indications for surgery, treatment was carried out according to the scheme (1st day - 1000 mg of cyclophosphane and 1000 mg of methylprednisolone (Solu-Medrol) intravenously per 150 ml of saline solution, heparin 5000 IU / k every 6 hours (4 times a day); on the 2nd and 3rd days, 1000 mg of methylprednisolone (Solu-Medrol) was administered intravenously, surgery was performed on the 7th day from the start of pulse therapy, and after surgery, starting from the 30th day, methotrexate was administered once a week at 15 mg (15 mg / week) in for 3 months, in the postoperative period, double anticoagulation therapy (antiplatelet + anticoagulant) acetylsalicylic acid (Cardiomagnil) was performed 75 mg / day and rivaroxaban (Xarelto) 20 mg / day daily, starting from 1 day and for 3 months.

Depending on the course of NAA, after 3 months of treatment, the dose of methotrexate was reduced by 2.5 mg every 2 weeks. Anti-relapse courses were conducted 2 times a year. When prescribing methotrexate, folic acid preparations were always prescribed.

In group II, conservative therapy was limited in 65 patients, surgical interventions were performed in 76. Against the background of conservative treatment, disease progression was noted in 4 patients (6.1%), of which hemodynamically insignificant stenosis GDNSS developed in 1 (1.5%) and hemodynamically significant stenosis GDSS – in 3 (4.6%); after surgical treatment, disease progression was in 10 (13.1%) of patients, moreover, hemodynamically insignificant stenosis GDNSS developed in 1 (1.3%), hemodynamically significant stenosis GDSS – in 9 (11.8%) (Fig.2).

Fig. 2. Progression of NAA involving new segments and arteries in group II

The number of repeated hospitalizations in groups I and II also differed statistically significantly, amounting to 2.1 ± 0.1 and 1.1 ± 0.1 , respectively.

This was facilitated by the new principles of conservative treatment of NAA: all patients in the chronic stage who needed surgery were treated with Scheme No.4. All patients with acute and subacute stages were treated according to Scheme No. 2 and 3.

With a stable course of NAA, the dose of methotrexate was reduced by 2.5 mg every 2 weeks under the control of ESR and CRP. Anti-relapse courses were conducted 2 times a year.

The effectiveness of therapy was evaluated based on the study of clinical, laboratory and ultrasound parameters.

The clinical criteria for the effectiveness of pulse therapy were considered to be a decrease in fever, the disappearance of the arthritis clinic, the disappearance of skin rashes, and the disappearance of pain along the vessels.

The laboratory criteria for effectiveness were considered to be a decrease in the level of ESR and CRP during therapy.

Ultrasound criteria included a decrease in the thickness of the CMM and a change in the echogenicity of the artery wall, a decrease in areas with hypo- and isoechogenic properties.

We also attempted to determine the cut-off thresholds for some laboratory markers of inflammation in patients with NAA, depending on the results of treatment. We considered the absence of progression involving new domains and vessels in NAA to be a favorable outcome (intermediate point), the presence of progression to be unfavorable. As our observations showed,

the level of leukocytosis before the intervention, as well as the content of the acute phase protein fibrinogen, was not associated with the outcome of treatment, whereas for CRP and ESR, ROC analysis showed the presence of such a relationship, and the tests themselves can be regarded as informative in the prognosis of treatment.

These thresholds were as follows: ESR less than 32 mm/h, CRP less than 18 mg/l at AUC = 0.905 (sensitivity =81%, specificity =90%) and 0.902 (sensitivity =95%, specificity =75%), respectively, are associated with a favorable outcome of conservative treatment and surgery.

Fig.3. ROC analysis results

It should be noted that the average values of inflammation in groups I and II differed statistically significantly, while the decrease in CRP and ESR during treatment was more pronounced in group II (Table 1).

Table 1. The average values of inflammation in groups I and II before and after treatment

Parameter	I group			II group		
	Before	After	Δ, %	Before	After	Δ, %
WBC	15,1± 1,2	9,2± 0,7	49%	10,4± 0,19	6,7± 0,1	36%
CRP	28,0± 1,3	15,1± 0,4	47%	17,8± 0,7	10,8± 0,4	40%
ESR	50,1± 2,3	27,4± 1,1	46%	31,3± 0,9	18,5± 0,5	42%
Fibrinogen	3330± 67	2220±43	34%	3071± 86,0	2366± 39	23%

A decrease in ESR and CRP were associated with a favorable outcome of surgical treatment – with good late patency of shunts: the thresholds were as follows – ESR less than 21 mm/h, CRP less than 11 mg/l at AUC = 0.91 (sensitivity =90%, specificity =85%) and 0.88 (sensitivity =95%, specificity =80%), respectively (Fig. 4).

Fig.4. Results of ROC analysis - comparison of ROC curves for markers of inflammation after treatment in the prognosis of a favorable outcome of surgical treatment

In the long-term period after prolongation of pulse therapy with methotrexate, the level of CRP and ESR decreased to 6.58 ± 0.29 and 13.0 ± 0.35 in group II, whereas against the background of treatment with GCS in group I, these indicators were 9.0 ± 0.4 and 18.4 ± 0.5 , respectively, statistically significantly different from the parameters in group I.

Based on these criteria, threshold levels for laboratory remission of NAA were proposed: ESR is less than 21 mm/h, CRP is less than 11 mg/l at AUC = 0.91 (sensitivity =90%, specificity =85%) and 0.88 (sensitivity =95%, specificity =80%), respectively.

Discussion. Analyzing the results of treatment in group 1, we identified 3 important aspects: 1) surgical intervention provoked the progression of the disease, possibly due to the fact that it was carried out against the background of permanent inflammation, 2) existing criteria (criteria of A.V. Pokrovsky, ESR, CRP, ultrasound-DS data) do not allow to accurately detail the intensity of inflammation in NAA, 3) GCS therapy did not lead to the desired anti-inflammatory effect in patients with acute and subacute stage of NAA. In this regard, it became obvious that 1) optimization of preoperative preparation is necessary to effectively stop the activity of the inflammatory process, 2) it is necessary to develop a scheme for conservative treatment of NAA, including in the postoperative period to prevent the progression of the disease.

Considering the fact that in case of NAA, signs of all stages of the process may be present simultaneously in different parts of the vessel – from active inflammation with blurred wall contours and poor differentiation of the intima/media complex according to ultrasound-DS data to extended stenotic thickening and perivascular granulomatous process, in group II we not only evaluated the stage of the process, but used the appointment a short course of pulse therapy before surgery for hospitalization of patients in the chronic stage of the disease. After the operation, conservative treatment was continued.

The results of treatment in group II convinced us that the main principles of conservative therapy of patients with NAA-VDA are: the appointment of high doses of cyclophosphane and methylprednisolone during the first 3 days (pulse therapy), prolongation of methotrexate therapy for a long time, mainly subcutaneous administration in the first 3 months, a combination of administration of heparin 20,000 IU / day in the first 3 days followed by the introduction of dual antithrombotic therapy (acetylsalicylic acid + rivaroxaban). If the first course of pulse therapy is ineffective, the second and third courses of pulse therapy are carried out with an interval of 7 days, maintenance therapy with methotrexate is mandatory. Surgical treatment should be performed no earlier than 3 months after stabilization of laboratory parameters of inflammation, at the stage of

morphological remission, and not immediately after a course of pulse therapy. All patients in the chronic stage of NAA receive pulse therapy in the hospital before surgery, and after surgery, methotrexate prolongation (from the 30th day after surgery) and double antithrombotic therapy for 3 months are performed. After dynamic monitoring, the continuation of treatment is decided individually.

Thus, we believe that it is necessary to determine the stage of the process according to clinical and laboratory signs, however, given the diversity and multiplicity of lesions in NAA, all patients with a chronic stage should undergo pulse therapy in a hospital before surgery, and if there is no need for surgery, pulse therapy and methotrexate for 3 months. All patients with diagnosed acute and subacute stages should receive pulse therapy and methotrexate parenterally for at least 3 months, after which they can be operated on. This indicates that in NAA, inflammation is permanent, but expressed to varying degrees, and the chronic stage is conditional. Threshold levels for laboratory remission of NAA: ESR is less than 21 mm/h, CRP is less than 11 mg/l at AUC = 0.91 (sensitivity =90%, specificity =85%) and 0.88 (sensitivity =95%, specificity =80%), respectively. This strategy has made it possible to stabilize inflammation, control the disease and prevent complications.

Conclusions.

1. Evidence was obtained on the effectiveness of pulse therapy at any stage of NAA, which proved 1) the permanence of inflammation and the conditionality of the chronic stage, 2) the negative effect of surgery without prior pulse therapy, since the progression of NAA against the background of pulse therapy decreased 4.3 times with conservative (from 26.3% to 6.1%) and 3.8 times (from 49.4% to 13.1%) during surgical treatment.

2. The treatment strategy for all patients with NAA consists in prescribing pulse therapy with cyclophosphane and methylprednisolone: both in the chronic stage and in the presence of indications for surgery, as well as in the acute and subacute stages.

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